

Semi-automatic deposition of oriented Cu(OH)₂ nanobelts for the heteroepitaxial growth of Metal-Organic Framework films

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Abstract

Processing oriented metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) as thin films is a key challenge to for their application to device fabrication. However, typical fabrication methods cannot generate precisely oriented crystals on commercially relevant scales (i.e. cm²). This limits access to applications that require anisotropic functional properties (e.g. separation, optics, and electronics). Recently, highly oriented copper-based MOFs have been synthesized via the addition of the organic MOF component to an ethanolic solution of manually aligned Cu(OH)₂ nanobelt films. In this work we report the optimization of a semi-automatic method that affords a 100% yield of high quality ceramic films, at the cm scale, for the fabrication of precisely oriented MOF coatings. This improved fabrication protocol will facilitate the progress of heteroepitaxially grown MOFs for molecular separators and micro-opto-electronic devices.

Introduction

Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs) are extended solids consisting of inorganic nodes interconnected by organic linkers [1,2]. Both linkers and nodes are chemically mutable and their judicious selection yields porous crystals [1,2] with properties that are of interest to diverse technological applications. For example, MOFs have been applied to areas including molecular separation [3], sensing [4], electronics [4], and optics [5]. For some of these applications, supported MOF films are required, thus the development of fabrication methods for the deposition of homogenous MOF films with tunable scale, thickness, and roughness is an area of current interest [6,7]. Successful fabrication protocols include layer-by-layer, drop-/spin-casting, and vapor-phase depositions [6–9]. However, all these deposition methods lack precise control over the pore orientation as they produce MOF films with disordered alignment along one or more crystalline directions [7]. For some applications, the precise orientation of MOF channels across an entire film could lead to an enhancement in functionality [7,10–12]. For example, the pore alignment can confer a beneficial anisotropy for charge and mass transport [13–15], or for the orientation of guest molecules [10,11]; these aspects could enhance the performance of molecular separators, chemical sensors, and micro-opto-electronic devices [16,17].

Inspired by microelectronic fabrication methods, we recently demonstrated that inorganic crystalline materials can act as template systems for the fabrication of oriented MOF films [10,11]. The heteroepitaxial growth of MOFs on a ceramic material was demonstrated by exposing crystalline $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ nanostructures to an ethanolic solution of a ligand (Benzene-1,4-dicarboxylic acid, H_2BDC) [10]. This ceramic-to-MOF conversion, releases Cu^{2+} cations from $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ that are rapidly coordinated by the ligand in solution. Within minutes, crystalline $\text{Cu}_2(\text{BDC})_2$ forms and its lattice is precisely aligned to the lattice of the $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ nanobelts (NBs). By using a film of aligned $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ NBs the fabrication of precisely aligned and uniform Cu-based MOF films of 1 cm^2 was achieved. We note that both crystalline alignment and homogeneity are crucial parameters in film processing; [18] these general requirements are also highly desirable for the progress of MOF positioning technologies [4]. Specifically, the steps required for the fabrication of heteroepitaxial MOF films are: i) the controlled injection of the NB dispersion in a rectangular basin (**Figure 1 a, b**), ii) the self-orientation of the NBs in the basin (**Figure 1 c, d**), and iii) the manual transfer of the NBs from the surface of the basin to a desired substrate (e.g. silicon, **Figure 1 e-g**). The subsequent exposure of the aligned NB coating to the ligand in solution yields the polycrystalline MOF film with precise 3D orientation (**Figure 1 h**). XRD data (**Figures 1 i-k**) demonstrate that the alignment of the $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ NBs influences the final $\text{Cu}_2(\text{BDC})_2$ film orientation: the azimuthal angle dependence of $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ (002) and $\text{Cu}_2(\text{BDC})_2$ (100) diffraction peak intensities show similar patterns (**Figures 1 j, k**). [10] Thus, the fabrication of highly ordered $\text{Cu}_2(\text{BDC})_2$ MOF coatings requires the deposition of highly ordered $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ NB films.

However, there are shortcomings in the fabrication protocol of these aligned Cu-based MOF films. Due to the manual transfer procedure, the quality of the oriented $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ NB film in terms of homogeneity and crystalline alignment was inconsistent from operator to operator and, most importantly, from sample

to sample. For example, we qualitatively estimated that only 50% of the samples manually deposited by a trained operator have sufficient quality to be converted into oriented MOF films. To quantify the yield, we decided to study 15 NB films manually deposited on silicon. For each sample, we measured: 1) the homogeneity of the film quantifying the surface coated by the NBs (vide infra), 2) the azimuthal angle dependence of the XRD intensity profile (full width at half maximum, FWHM) from which we calculated a parameter α that can be correlated to the angular distribution of the NBs (vide infra). The result is shown in **Figure 1 l**: only 7 out of 15 samples have high quality (homogeneity measured as coverage % > 95% and orientation > 0.65, vide infra for the precise understanding of these parameters). This analysis demonstrates that the current manual deposition is a bottle neck in the preparation of oriented MOF films and a more effective deposition method is needed.

Motivated by our interest in expanding this area of research and facilitating the implementation of heteroepitaxially grown MOFs for technological applications, we developed a semi-automatic protocol for the deposition of oriented $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ NB films utilizing a dip-coater (**Figure 1 m**). The data confirm the superior quality of the films prepared with the semi-automatic fabrication protocol. We optimized variables involved in the automatic transfer step (levelling, deposition speed, and immersion depth) of the $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ NBs from the solution to the substrate and evaluated their influence by assessing the homogeneity (coverage %) and preferential alignment of the $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ film on crystalline silicon substrates. In addition, we optimised the injection volume of the $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ NBs solution. We compared the quality of the films we fabricated by the optimized deposition protocol to those films prepared using the manual deposition method. In summary, our semi-automatic deposition protocol: i) improved the average film orientation and homogeneity, ii) provided a 100% yield of high quality coatings, and iii) enhanced scalability of NB films from 1 cm² to 10 cm². Beyond the application to $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ NBs, the developed deposition protocol has the potential to align a number of one-dimensional (1D) nanostructures for optical, electronic and energy applications [19].

High yield of poorly aligned MOF films

High yield of well aligned MOF films

Figure 1: Schematic of the steps involved in the controlled deposition of oriented $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ nanobelt (NB) films. a) The deposition starts with a basin filled with water, then b) an ethanolic dispersion of $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ NBs is injected on the water surface with a syringe. c) The NBs align during the injection, and d) injection continues until the water surface is fully covered with the NB dispersion. e) Once the aligned NB film is present in the basin, a substrate is manually immersed and the NBs are transferred on a support (e.g. silicon). g) Schematic of a typical film obtained by the manual procedure, and h) the corresponding films converted to MOF. i) X-ray diffraction patterns of $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ NB films and the corresponding $\text{Cu}_2(\text{BDC})_2$ MOF coatings obtained by the ceramic-to-MOF conversion. j) Azimuthal scan of the intensity of the (002) diffraction peak of $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ for three samples with different orientation degree, designated as low ($\alpha=0.53$), medium ($\alpha=0.64$) and high ($\alpha=0.78$) orientation. k) Azimuthal scan of the intensity of the (100) diffraction peak of $\text{Cu}_2(\text{BDC})_2$ of the same samples after conversion to MOF, also show a corresponding low ($\alpha=0.49$), medium ($\alpha=0.64$) and high ($\alpha=0.77$) orientation. l) Typical distribution of NBs obtained by the manual procedure when performed by different operators. The right axis refers to the width (σ of Gaussian fits) of the azimuthal X-ray scans. σ_z is equivalent to the distribution of crystallite orientations as calculated for 2D Gaussian distributions of polycrystalline $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ NB assemblies (see Supporting Information, Section 5). Selected samples in shades of green correspond to the azimuthal dependence data shown in j) with low, medium and high orientation. m) Scheme of the semi-automatic deposition setup replacing the manual transfer. n) Schematic of the expected NB films obtained by the semi-automatic protocol, and o) the corresponding films converted to MOF.

Figure 2: a) SEM micrograph of a typical $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ NB film obtained by the manual procedure showing a disordered region, b) SEM micrograph of a typical manual sample converted to $\text{Cu}_2(\text{BDC})_2$ MOF showing an ordered region. c, d) AFM 3D topography images of a representative region of a $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ NB film before and after conversion to $\text{Cu}_2(\text{BDC})_2$. e) FTIR spectra of the $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ NB film and the $\text{Cu}_2(\text{BDC})_2$ oriented MOF film.

Experimental

Synthesis of Copper hydroxide nanobelts (NBs) and manual deposition

$\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ nanobelts (NBs) were synthesized following the literature procedure [10,20]: starting from a 0.04 M $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ aqueous solution (10 ml), 3 ml of 0.15 M NH_4OH were added dropwise under stirring, resulting in a deep blue solution. After 5 minutes of continuous stirring, 0.6 ml of a 12 M NaOH aqueous solution was added dropwise, resulting in a light blue precipitate. The stirring continued for 1 hour at room temperature. Afterwards, a 30 min thermal treatment at 40 °C (closed flask, without stirring) was performed, and the powders were centrifuged and washed with water (1 x 20 ml) and ethanol (2 x 20 ml). Thus, 0.3 g of wet $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ nanobelts were obtained (corresponding to 0.039 g of dried NBs), and dispersed in 10 ml of ethanol.

Oriented $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ films were prepared from these ethanolic solutions of NBs by a protocol illustrated in **Figure 1** [10]: i) a 63×34×10 mm (internal dimensions) epoxy-acrylate 3D-printed basin was filled with 13.8 ml of DI water (**Figure 1 a**); ii) the nanobelts were injected on the water surface using a syringe pump (KD Scientific, Norm-Ject™ 1 ml syringe, 0.45 x 25 mm BL/LB Sterican™ needles) with a flow rate of 0.18 ml min⁻¹ (**Figure 1 a**); iii) the injection proceeded until an homogeneous layer of NBs was uniformly coating the water surface (**Figure 1 c, d**); vi) a substrate, typically silicon, was manually approached to the surface of the water bath, pressed on the nanobelt film with a quick motion and promptly removed from the water bath (**Figure 1 e, f**); v) the $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ NB coatings were rinsed with ethanol and dried under nitrogen or compressed air flux; vi) the ceramic films were converted to $\text{Cu}_2(\text{BDC})_2$ by immersing them in 10 ml of a 0.1 mg ml⁻¹ solution of H_2BDC in a mixture of ethanol (7.14 ml, 99.8% purity) and water (2.86 ml). After 10 minutes the samples were removed, rinsed thoroughly with ethanol and then dried. The resulting films were characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM, VEGA 3 - Tescan), atomic force microscopy (AFM, Cypher ES - Oxford Instruments) and Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR, ALPHA - Bruker) (**Figure 2**) to examine morphology and chemical composition. The SEM images show the 1D morphology of $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ NBs deposited with the manual procedure (**Figure 2 a**) and the $\text{Cu}_2(\text{BDC})_2$ crystals grown perpendicularly to the NB main axis. From AFM analysis, the average dimensions of the nanobelts were 30 nm wide and 230 nm long (**Figure 2 c** and **Figure S1**, Supporting Information), and the change of the surface roughness confirm the ceramic-to-MOF conversion, showing elongated particles oriented perpendicularly to the NBs direction (**Figure 2 d**). The IR spectra (**Figure 2 e**) show vibrational modes that can be ascribed to the $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ NBs coating (Cu-O vibrations below 700 cm⁻¹; hydroxyl ions at

3310 and 3570 cm^{-1}) [21] and to the $\text{Cu}_2(\text{BDC})_2$ films (asymmetric and symmetric carboxylate vibrations at 1569 and 1400 cm^{-1}) [22]. The crystal structure of $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ NBs and $\text{Cu}_2(\text{BDC})_2$ films were investigated using out-of-plane XRD (**Figure 1 i**; Rigaku Smart Lab, 9 kW rotating anode, $\lambda = 0.154$ nm) and confirmed the previously reported crystal structures ($\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ showed reflections at 16.7°, 23.8°, and 34.08° that are assigned to (020) (021) and (002) planes; $\text{Cu}_2(\text{BDC})_2$ showed reflections at 8.24°, 16.7° that are assigned to (100) and (200) planes; peaks at 30.28°, 30.47°, 32.96° and 33.04° are ascribed to the Si substrate) [10]. The influence of the alignment of the $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ NBs on the final $\text{Cu}_2(\text{BDC})_2$ film orientation is experimentally demonstrated correlating the XRD data (**Figures 1 i, j, k**) of the two films. The in-plane (incident angle: $\omega=0.2^\circ$) azimuthal angle dependence of intensity profile of the (002) reflection of $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ at a diffraction angle of 34.08° show two maxima separated by 180° (**Figure 1 j**; **Figure S4**, Supporting Information). The (100) reflection of $\text{Cu}_2(\text{BDC})_2$ at a diffraction angle of 8.24° shows the same azimuthal angle dependence of intensity profile (**Figure 1 k**; **Figure S4**, Supporting Information). Overall, material characterization confirms that the here prepared $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ NBs and $\text{Cu}_2(\text{BDC})_2$ films have the same morphology, crystalline diffraction patterns and chemical composition of those reported in previous studies for the heteroepitaxial conversion into Cu-based MOFs [10–12].

Deposition procedure with the use of a dip-coater.

With the aim to overcome the low yields achieved via manual fabrication, we here introduce the use of a dip coater for the fabrication of the $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ NB films (**Figure 1m** – semi-automatic protocol). First, the relative position between the needle and water basin was chosen by assessing the film quality with an optical microscope (**Figure S2**, Supporting Information). When injecting the NB dispersion in the water-filled basin, the time required to form a full film on the water surface was first assessed visually through the change in opacity, and set to be 21 s at 0.18 ml min^{-1} injection rate. This injection time corresponds to an injected volume of $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ NBs solution of 63 μl . Then, to deposit NB films on a substrate, a squared silicon wafer piece was fixed on a planar sample holder and lowered with immersion speed v_s , until the substrate was immersed into the NBs solution with a depth d_s , and then immediately withdrawn at the same speed v_s . The deposited NB films were rinsed with EtOH and dried with N_2 .

We studied variables related to the automatic transfer of the $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ NBs from the solution to the substrate such as levelling of the sample holder, immersion depth d_s and deposition speed v_s . Then, we optimised the injected volume of NBs solution in the basin. The influence of these variables on the resulting quality of the films was assessed by measurements of the homogeneity as coverage % of the silicon substrate and crystalline preferential orientation of the $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ films (**Figure 3**).

For both manual and semi-automatic protocols, the NBs solutions were vortexed for 30 s at 2400 RPM prior to every deposition to prevent obstruction of the syringe and needle. Silicon substrates were washed with ethanol and dried in N_2 prior to usage. All deposition steps were performed at ambient conditions at relative humidity (RH) in the 20-40% range (a prior study on the influence of RH did not suggest a

correlation between RH% and the quality of the NB films - data not shown). All the reported studies for the optimization of relevant parameters were performed on 1.5 cm x 1.5 cm silicon substrates (p-type, 10 Ohm cm) with (100) orientation.

Film quality (homogeneity and orientation)

The homogeneity of the films, here plotted as coverage %, was evaluated measuring the different reflectivity of the deposited film and the silicon substrate. We noted that the surface roughness of the areas coated with NBs is similar in all investigated samples. By providing the same homogeneous illumination for all the samples, the procedure can be used to assess the film homogeneity. Using a CMOS camera and a uniform LED illumination, pictures of the samples were converted to a binary image setting a threshold of 30% of the highest brightness (same threshold for all the images) and the effective coverage percentage was evaluated as bright pixels/total pixels (**Figure S3**, Supporting Information) taken in 1.3 x 1.3 cm² areas. This method offers a quantitative value of the macroscopic film coverage.

The preferential crystalline orientation of the films was characterised by in-plane X-ray diffraction (**Figure S4**, Supporting Information). Azimuthal scans were performed following the (002) reflection of Cu(OH)₂ at an angle of $2\theta=34.08^\circ$. The azimuthal data were fit with a Gaussian function and the full width at half maximum (FWHM) was determined for both peaks and averaged. A normalized parameter was introduced to evaluate the orientation, based on the equation $\alpha = 1 - f \pi^{-1}$, where f is the FWHM in radians [23–25]. This parameter has a maximum theoretical value of 1 (full orientation) and is commonly used to study the orientation of anisotropic carbon materials [23,26]. As an alternative approach, we considered a 2D analogue to the Herman's orientation function [27] to quantify directional order (see Supporting Information, Section 5). This order parameter, S^{2D} , has for example been used to describe order in 2D nematic liquid crystals [28,29]. S^{2D} has the advantage that it assumes values between 0 (isotropic system) and 1 (fully oriented system) and is more useful than α when characterizing very poorly aligned samples (Supporting Information **Figure S5**). For the films studied here, samples have a sufficient degree of orientation, α and S^{2D} yield the same trends (see Supporting Information **Figure S6**). In the main manuscript, we will rely on α in the plots due to its more practical correlation with the FWHM from the azimuthal scans.

With the purpose of correlating α with the physical orientation of the NBs on the substrate, we calculated the expected width of an azimuthal XRD scan associated with the (002) reflection of Cu(OH)₂ from the width of the actual distribution of the NBs. These calculations were based on an assembly of Cu(OH)₂ crystallites assuming planarity of the nanobelts with the lattice vector \vec{b} being perpendicular to the surface. As a measure of the in-plane alignment of the nanobelts, we assumed the orientation angles of the long nanobelts axis, ζ , to be distributed according to Gaussian distributions with widths (standard deviations) σ_ζ . These calculations show that over a wide range of crystallite sizes and α -values the

widths of the peaks of the azimuthal scans and of the actual crystallite distributions are identical. Thus, the experimentally determined α is directly connected to σ_ζ via $\sigma_\zeta = \frac{\pi(1-\alpha)}{2\sqrt{2} \ln 2} = 1.334 (1 - \alpha)$ (see Supporting Information, Section 6, **Figure 3 c**, and Supporting Information **Figure S8**).

Figure 3: Schematic representation of the parameters used to characterize the quality of the Cu(OH)₂ NB films. a) Orientation versus coverage for three model cases of low [$\alpha=0.4$, 70%], medium [$\alpha=0.575$, 82%] and high quality [$\alpha=0.75$, 95%]. The right-hand axis provides the conversion to the calculated angular distribution of the physical NB system from our model (Supporting Information **Figure S8**). b) Diagrams representing model samples with a coverage of 70%, 82% and 95% (Cu(OH)₂ NB film in green, silicon substrate in orange). c) Schemes representing the possible deviations from the NBs with respect to the preferential orientation corresponding to the different angular distributions associated to each value of α (0.4 corresponding to $\pm 45^\circ$, 0.575 corresponding to $\pm 32^\circ$, and 0.75 corresponding to $\pm 18^\circ$).

Figure 4: a, b) Schematic of the levelling procedure. c) Average coverage and e) orientation obtained from 10 samples deposited by the automatic transfer before and after a levelling procedure that brings the substrate parallel to the surface of the liquid in the basin.

Results and discussion

The deposition of oriented and homogeneous $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ films underpins the fabrication of heteroepitaxially oriented Cu-based MOF films. Until now, the fabrication of oriented $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ was obtained exclusively through a manual procedure yielding operator-dependent results and, as a result, low reproducibility. Based on our experiments, only ca. 50% of the $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ NB films were sufficiently oriented and homogeneous (**Figure 1 I**). To overcome the issue of low yields, we introduced a semi-automatic deposition and employed a dip-coater to transfer the $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ NBs from the surface of the solution to the silicon substrate. By improving reproducibility, we anticipated that we could identify and optimise relevant variables of this new deposition system. To this end, we investigated deposition variables including levelling, immersion depth (d_s), immersion speed (v_s) and injected volume of the NB dispersion.

Initially, we adopted the same parameters used for literature reported $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ NBs depositions for oriented MOF films [10], see Experimental section. The homogeneity of the films (ranging from 0 (no coverage) to 100% (full coverage)) was evaluated in terms of the surface coverage %, calculated using the optical method described in the Experimental section. The orientation of the NB films was evaluated by the parameter α , see Experimental section, which is valued at 1 for fully oriented samples and decreases monotonically with decreasing orientation. For each point reported in the plots, the values of surface coverage and orientation of the films are the average values and standard deviation of triplicates.

The first parameter we studied was the influence of the sample levelling with respect to the horizontal plane of the basin. This is schematically shown in **Figure 4 a, b**. To proceed with a typical one-factor at-the-time approach,[30] we fixed the values of $d_s=1.3$ mm and $v_s=3.5$ mm s^{-1} . The data show that the sample levelling had a distinct influence on both sample homogeneity and orientation (**Figure 4 c, d**). Indeed, the example of tilting angles above 0.6° of the substrate with respect to the horizontal plane produced films with cracks and macroscopic inhomogeneous regions (**Figure S9**, Supporting Information). However, by reducing the tilting angle to $\leq 0.6^\circ$, homogeneity significantly improved preventing the cracks that were observed for larger tilting. The improved film homogeneity is demonstrated by the improved average coverage = $96\% \pm 4\%$ (**Figure 4 c** and Supporting Information **Figure S9**). A further reduction of the tilting angle down to 0° (i.e. perfect levelling) led to a slight improvement in the homogeneity that increased to $98\% \pm 1\%$. Interestingly, in terms of the average orientation, the unlevelled samples exhibit a mean $\alpha = 0.64 \pm 0.04$, similar to the value obtained by the manual procedure ($\alpha=0.65 \pm 0.10$). For a 0° tilting angle, the average orientation obtained was increased to 0.72 ± 0.03 (**Figure 4 d**). Thus, to increase the average orientation (12.5% improvement), levelling with a precision below 200 μm of tilting gap was required to obtain a sufficiently parallel substrate (silicon, 1.5 cm x 1.5 cm). The use of the dip-coater allowed us to identify a major parameter that has

an important influence on the homogeneity, average orientation and reproducibility. Importantly, this parameter cannot be precisely controlled via manual deposition.

Next we studied the immersion depth (d_s) and samples were produced with varying depths between 0 and 2.5 mm with respect to the surface of the liquid in the basin (**Figure 5 a, b**). Levelling was applied to each substrate with a fixed deposition speed of $v_s=3.5 \text{ mm s}^{-1}$. From the study of d_s , we found that immersion depths below 1 mm and above 2 mm produced coatings with cracks and/or bubbles resulting in inconsistent homogeneity as shown by the large error bars of **Figure 5a**. From this plot, when d_s increases from 1 mm to 2 mm, a progressive decrease of the variability is measured. Taking into consideration the orientation a d_s value of 1.5 mm was selected: this immersion depth showed coverage of $98.3\% \pm 0.7\%$ and the highest orientation of 0.74 ± 0.04 .

By setting 0° tilting (perfect levelling) and $d_s=1.5 \text{ mm}$, we studied the influence of deposition speed in the range $1 \text{ mm s}^{-1} \leq v_s \leq 10 \text{ mm s}^{-1}$ (**Figure 5 c,d**). A maximum speed of 10 mm s^{-1} was chosen as a further increase led to vibrations resulting in the instability of our deposition method. For $v_s < 3.5 \text{ mm s}^{-1}$ we found the deposited samples showed poor and inconsistent homogeneity. Interestingly, varying v_s over the entire speed range, resulted in a marginal improvement in orientation (i.e. 2.4%). However, for higher speeds, we observed a progressive improvement in the reproducibility related to α (see error bars in **Figure 5d**). From these data, we chose $v_s=10 \text{ mm s}^{-1}$ as this afforded a homogeneity of $99.7\% \pm 0.2\%$ and an orientation of 0.74 ± 0.02 . This v_s afforded the highest reproducibility within the investigated deposition speeds.

With a fixed v_s value of 10 mm s^{-1} we varied the injected volume of the $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ NB dispersion between $36 \mu\text{l}$ and $90 \mu\text{l}$. By increasing the injected volume, we measured a consistent improvement in the film homogeneity and reproducibility, which plateaued at ca. 95% for an injected volume $\geq 63 \mu\text{l}$ (**Figure 5 e**). The plot **Figure 5 f** shows the effect of the injected volume of NBs solution in the mean orientation value. A significant increase of the orientation and an improved reproducibility are measured from $\alpha = 0.63 \pm 0.03$ ($36 \mu\text{l}$) to $\alpha = 0.75 \pm 0.01$ ($69 \mu\text{l}$), the latter exhibiting the highest orientation of the set. Larger injected volumes result in a loss of orientation. Thus, with the highest orientation and a measured coverage of $99.3\% \pm 0.5\%$, an injection volume of $69 \mu\text{l}$ was selected as the optimised value.

Figure 5: Coverage (a, c, e) and orientation (b, d, f) values for the samples prepared by varying immersion depth, deposition speed and injected volume of $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ NBs solution. The experiments were performed in triplicates, mean values are indicated in the scatter plots, and error bars correspond to the standard deviation.

Figure 6 a and **6 b** show the influence of each studied parameter on the average coverage, average orientation and reproducibility (error bars) of the NB films. The average homogeneity of the films was improved from 91% (original manual protocol) to 99.4%. Simultaneously, a substantially increased reproducibility in the coverage of the films was observed as a progressive reduction of the standard deviation from 9% to 0.3%. The mean orientation was increased from $\alpha = 0.65$ (original manual procedure) to $\alpha = 0.75$ for the semi-automatic procedure under the optimised conditions. The reproducibility in the orientation was also improved, with a decrease of the standard deviation of α by an order of magnitude (from 0.10 for manual deposition to 0.01 for semi-automatic deposition). To compare the quality and reproducibility of the manual protocol with the here optimised semi-automatic protocol, a set of 10 samples were prepared via the semi-automatic deposition and compared to the manually deposited samples (**Figure 6 c**).

Figure 6 c shows the significant improvement afforded by the semi-automatic protocol for homogeneity, average orientation and reproducibility of the deposited NB films. We found that 100% of the samples produced with the semi-automatic method have coverage above 95% and orientation above 0.7, while only 30% of the manual samples fall in this area (**Figures 6 c**).

The semi-automatic protocol was tested for the sequential deposition of multiple layers of $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ NBs to obtain thick (~800 nm) $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ NB films (Supporting Information, **Figure S10**). This procedure is extremely challenging to perform manually due to the lack of reproducibility of the manual deposition method and typically yields very poor overall orientation in multilayered films (e.g., five $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ NB layers showed $\alpha=0.42$, Supporting Information **Figure S10 e**). The use of the semi-automatic protocol led to a 1.35-fold increase of the multiple layers $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ NB film orientation (Supporting Information, **Figure S10 e**).

Finally, we tested the semi-automatic protocol for the preparation of oriented films on different large substrates (Si wafers up to 10 cm^2 and soda-lime glasses up to 7.5 cm^2 , **Figure 6 d, e** and **Figure S11** in Supporting Information). With this procedure we deposited oriented NB films with area 10-fold larger than previously reported [10], with homogeneity up to 99% and orientation $\alpha=0.62$. When comparing these values with the ones measured from NB films deposited with the manual method (coverage=91% and $\alpha=0.48$) the here proposed semi-automatic protocol afforded a 9% improvement in the coating and 30% improvement in the orientation.

a silicon substrate. We defined criteria to quantify the alignment of the NBs and the NB film homogeneity per each sample. We screened deposition variables and found that a perfect levelling of the silicon substrate with respect to the basin is crucial. For the deposition of high quality films, immersion depths and speed, and injected volume of the nanobelts solution should be set as 1.5 mm, 10 mm s⁻¹, 69 µl respectively, for a basin of 63×34×10 mm (internal dimensions). With these values we have increased the yield of high-quality films from ca. 50% to 100%, and further improved the ease of preparation of these oriented ceramic films. This improved average film quality and reproducibility will expand the scope of heteroepitaxially grown MOFs. In addition, this semi-automatic protocol affords the fabrication of films of 10 cm², with a 10-fold enlargement with respect to the previous samples. Such control over the orientation and homogeneity of the NB films will progress the application of MOFs films with anisotropic properties.

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